

IQTISODIYOT va TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

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IQTISODIYOTNI RAQAMLASHTIRISH:
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XORIJIY TAJRIBA**

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KIRISH SO‘ZI

HURMATLI ANJUMAN ISHTIROKCHILARI, MEHMONLAR, HAMKASBLAR, AZIZ TALABALAR!

Sizlarni Toshkent menejment va iqtisodiyot instituti tomonidan tashkil etilayotgan mazkur Respublika ilmiy-amaliy anjumanida qutlashdan mamnunmiz.

Qadrli anjuman ishtirokchilari, bugun biz mamlakatimizda biznesni qo‘llab-quvvatlash va iqtisodiyotni raqamlashtirish masalalari bo‘yicha amalga oshirilayotgan ishlar, mavjud muammolar va ularni bartaraf etish yo‘llari, hamda bu yo‘nalishdagi xorijiy tajribalarni muhokama qilish uchun to‘plandik.

Habaringiz bor, Prezidentimiz tomonidan 2024-yilni O‘zbekistonda “Yoshlar va biznesni qo‘llab-quvvatlash yili”, deb e‘lon qilinganida, inson qadrini ulug‘lash va aholimiz manfaatlarini ta‘minlash uchun kuchli iqtisodiyot barpo etish asosiy vazifalarimizdan biri ekanligi ta‘kidlangan edi.

Shunga ko‘ra, joriy yilda iqtisodiyotimizga xorijiy investitsiyalarni jalb etishga, tadbirkorlik va xususiy mulk uchun keng imkoniyatlar yaratishga, ilm-fan, innovatsiya, IT kabi sohalarni, “yashil” va raqamli texnologiyalarni rivojlantirishga alohida e‘tibor qaratilmoqda.

Chunki, barqaror va kuchli iqtisodiyot nafaqat iqtisodiyot subyektlari uchun, balki jamiyatimizning kelajagi va farovonligi uchun ham juda katta ahamiyatga ega.

Hozirgi kunda, bizning jamiyatimiz - raqamli transformatsiya davriga qadam qo‘ydi. Raqamlashtirish jarayoni - biznes jarayonlaridan tortib, davlat xizmatlariga qadar ko‘plab sohalarni qamrab olmoqda.

Albatta bunday o‘zgarishlar, texnologik taraqqiyotga hamohang ravishda, qo‘shimcha imkoniyatlarni ochishga va rivojlanishning yangi strategiyalarini ishlab chiqishga keng imkoniyatlar yaratmoqda.

Lekin shu bilan bir qatorda, iqtisodiyotni raqamlashtirish va bunday sharoitda biznesni rivojlantirish jarayonlarida, o‘ziga xos muammolar va turli savollar ham yuzaga kelmoqda.

Bunday masalalarni o‘rganib, uning yechimlarini topish uchun Toshkent menejment va iqtisodiyot institutining professor-o‘qituvchilari tomonidan ham turli ilmiy tadqiqotlarni olib borish yo‘lga qo‘yilgan. Ularning tadqiqotlari natijalaridan - o‘quv jarayonlarida, ta‘lim sifatini oshirish maqsadlarida, keng foydalaniladi.

Bu o‘z navbatida, institutda menejment, iqtisodiyot va axborot texnologiyalari sohasida tayyorlanadigan malakali mutaxassislarining nafaqat nazariy bilimlarini, balki amaliy ko‘nikmalarini ham oshirishga hizmat qiladi.

Bundan tashqari, institutda innovatsion dasturlar va loyihalar orqali talabalarni yangi texnologiyalar bilan tanishtirish, ularda raqamli iqtisodiyot va global biznes muhitida raqobatbardosh bo‘lish uchun zarur bo‘lgan ko‘nikmalarni shakllantirishga yordam beradi.

Bugungi anjumanda, biz raqamlashtirish va biznesni rivojlantirish jarayonlarida uchraydigan muammolarni chuqur o‘rganishni va ilmiy asoslangan yechimlarni izlashni o‘z oldimizga maqsad qilib qo‘yganmiz.

Shu bilan birga, asosiy anjuman va sho‘ba yig‘ilishlarida mazkur masalalar bo‘yicha xorijiy tajribalarni ham tahlil qilish orqali, biz qanday yechimlar topishimiz mumkinligini muhokama qilamiz.

Bugun sizlarning e‘tiboringizga taqdim etiladigan taqdimotlar va fikrlar - bizni zamonaviy iqtisodiyotning yangi talablariga mos keladigan biznes modellarni yaratishga ilhomlantiradi.

Maqsadimiz – bu kabi ilmiy-amaliy uchrashuvlar orqali ilm ahlini va biznes vakillarini bir joyda jamlab, biznesni qo‘llab-quvvatlash mexanizmlarini hamda iqtisodiyotni raqamlashtirish jarayonlarini yanada takomillashtirish bo‘yicha asoslangan takliflar va amaliy tavsiyalarni ishlab chiqishga imkoniyatlar yaratishdan iboratdir.

Biz bu jarayonda, o‘z tajribamizni almashish va birgalikda muammolarni hal qilish uchun yangi g‘oyalarni kashf etishni maqsad qilamiz.

Umid qilamanki, anjumanimiz samarali va foydali bo‘ladi.

Har biringizning ishtirokingiz va hissangiz bu jarayonda juda muhim.

Keling, birgalikda yangiliklarga ochiq bo‘lib, innovatsion yechimlarni izlaylik!

Bugungi anjuman ishiga va unda ishtirok etayotgan barcha ishtirokchilarning ilmiy-ijodiy faoliyatlariga ulkan muvaffaqiyatlar tilaymiz!

**Axmedov Xojiakbarxon Dilshatovich,
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3-SHO‘BA. **MOLIYA VA SOLIQ SOHASIDAGI MUAMMOLAR,** **YECHIMLAR VA XORIJIY TAJRIBALAR**

THE DETERMINANTS OF FINANCIAL DEVELOPMENT IN CASE OF CENTRAL ASIAN COUNTRIES

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu tadqiqot oddiy chiziqli regressiya usulidan foydalangan holda Markaziy Osiyoning to'rtta davlatida (Qozog'iston, Qirg'iziston, Tojikiston va O'zbekiston) moliyaviy rivojlanish determinantlarini o'rganishdan iborat. Har bir mamlakatda 2009 va 2023 yillardagi yillik panel ma'lumotlaridan foydalangan holda, tadqiqot moliyaviy rivojlanish, savdo ochiqligi, inflyatsiya, aholi jon boshiga YaIM daromadi, majburiy zaxira va davlat qarzlari o'rtasidagi bog'liqlikni aniqladi. Regressiya natijalari shuni ko'rsatadiki, savdo ochiqligi va majburiy zaxiralar tanlangan mamlakatlarda moliyaviy rivojlanishga salbiy va statistik jihatdan ahamiyatsiz ta'sir ko'rsatdi. Boshqa o'zgaruvchilar, masalan, inflyatsiya, aholi jon boshiga to'g'ri keladigan yalpi ichki mahsulot, davlat qarzlari moliyaviy rivojlanishga ijobiy ta'sir ko'rsatdi. Ushbu tadqiqotda banklarning yalpi ichki mahsulotdagi ulushidagi xususiy kreditlari moliyaviy rivojlanishning proksi sifatida ishlatiladi va markaziy banklarning qayta moliyalash stavkasi siyosat stavkasining proksi sifatida ham qo'llaniladi. Hukumatlar mamlakatlar o'rtasidagi savdo va zaxira talablari haqida qayg'urishi kerak, chunki bu operatsiyalar bank sohasiga bevosita va bilvosita ta'sir qiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: Markaziy Osiyo, OLS, Moliyaviy rivojlanish, Panel ma'lumotlari.

Abstract: This study purposes at investigating the determinants of financial development in four countries of Central Asia such as (Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Tajikistan and Uzbekistan) employing simple linear regression method. Utilizing panel data in annual from 2009 and 2023 in each country case, the study found a relationship between financial development, trade openness, inflation, GDP per capita income, reserve requirement and government borrowing. The outcome of regression reveals that, trade openness and reserve requirement exerted negative and statistically insignificant impacts on financial development in selected countries cases. While other variables such as, inflation, GDP per capita income, government borrowing represented positive influences on financial development. Private credit by banks in share of GDP is used as a proxy for financial development and refinancing rate of central banks is also used as a proxy for policy rate in this study. Governments need to care about trade between countries and reserve requirements since these transactions have direct and indirect effect on banking sphere.

Key words: Central Asia, OLS, Financial development, Panel data.

Аннотация: Целью данного исследования является изучение детерминант финансового развития в четырех странах Центральной Азии, таких как (Казахстан, Кыргызстан, Таджикистан и Узбекистан), с использованием метода простой линейной регрессии. Используя панельные данные за год с 2009 по 2023 год в каждом случае страны, исследование обнаружило связь между финансовым развитием, открытостью торговли, инфляцией, доходом ВВП на душу населения, обязательными резервами и государственными заимствованиями. Результат регрессии показывает, что открытость торговли и обязательные резервы оказали отрицательное и статистически незначимое влияние на финансовое развитие в случаях отдельных стран. В то время как другие переменные, такие как инфляция, доход ВВП на душу населения, государственные заимствования оказали положительное влияние на финансовое развитие. Частный кредит банков в доле ВВП используется в качестве прокси для финансового развития, а ставка рефинансирования центральных банков также используется в качестве прокси для учетной ставки в этом исследовании. Правительствам необходимо заботиться о торговле между странами и обязательных резервах, поскольку эти транзакции оказывают прямое и косвенное влияние на банковскую сферу.

Ключевые слова: Центральная Азия, OLS, Финансовое развитие, Панельные данные.

INTRODUCTION

The growth of the financial sector is essential to economic development and is widely regarded as a sign of a nation's prosperity (Svirydzhenka, 2016). But differences in how each nation's financial sector has developed

can cause a gap between advanced and developing countries. The gap in progress between emerging and developed nations is best illustrated by the Asian region, especially when it comes to the financial industry (Svirydzenka, 2016; Shen and Lin, 2007). Furthermore, the post-global financial crisis era suggests that Asian banking efficiency and liquidity must improve. This is because Asian banks outperform banks in other regions of the world, as noted by Vinayak et al. (2016), and as a result, they have a major influence on the viability and efficiency of the global banking system. Unexpectedly, Central Asian nations have experienced remarkable economic expansion since the year 2000. The combined gross domestic product (GDP) of Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Mongolia, Tajikistan, Turkmenistan, and Uzbekistan increased by 7% annually on average between 2000 and 2016 (OECD, 2018). The financial system has been sufficiently developed to support economic development at a different pace than the comparatively advanced economies of central and eastern Europe (Djalilov & Piesse, 2011). The production disparity appears to have closed between Central Asian nations and South Korea and Japan (Yormirzoev, 2021). Nonetheless, there is a tendency for the financial stability of Central Asian nations to deteriorate. For instance, the public's trust in Tajikistan's financial system's soundness was severely damaged by the country's 2015 financial collapse (OECD, 2018). In the meantime, financial stability has declined recently in other countries like Kyrgyz Republic, Kazakhstan, and Uzbekistan (World Bank, 2017). Meanwhile, since 2005, Central Asia's average bank penetration has declined, with Tajikistan and the Kyrgyz Republic making major contributions (World Bank, 2017). In fact, Fu et al. (2014) show that economic stability is enhanced by greater bank market dominance in Asia. In addition to financial liberalization, there are a number of other essential determinants which directly and indirectly influence on financial development in case of Central Asia countries. This paper is devoting to examine the impact of selected determinants of financial development and also contribute to enlargement of literature regarding to this study. In the following paragraphs, previously conducted papers are going to be reviewed in order to mention and employ as a role model in response to analyze the influence factor of determinants in terms of giving an inference. Since this study's empirical analysis is based on panel data analysis, information about econometric model is going to be delivered in methodology and in results paragraphs in the following sections of this study.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Five groups were created by the researchers to contain all endogenous and exogenous factors influencing financial progress. These include the government's intervention, institutions, legal customs, openness policies, and political economy variables (Voghoei et al., 2011). The accomplishments of a nation's financial industry can be ascertained by contrasting the levels of prices and quantities, especially the interest rate spread and stock flow. Numerous scholars employed various financial development parameters. Credit to private as a percentage of GDP was utilised, for example, by Scartascini (2012), Huang (2005), and Arcand et al. (2015). Conversely, liquid obligation (M2) as a proportion of GDP was employed by King and Levine (1993), Demetriades and Leuintel (1996), and Saci and Holden (2008).

The empirical research conducted by Mbulawa (2015) reveals compelling proof that trade openness, institutional characteristics, and economic expansion all contribute to the explanation of financial development, or the percentage of GDP attributed to credit to the private sector. Hofmann (2001) examined the factors influencing credit to the private non-bank sector using data from 16 industrialised nations. The researcher discovered that real interest rates had a detrimental impact on financial progress. Akinlo and Oni (2015) assert that the reserve ratio and prime lending rate contribute to a decline in credit in the private sector. Although real lending by banks to private companies tends to decline, inflation increases private credit to the private sector. Badeb and Lean (2017) investigated the primary factors influencing financial development in the Republic of Yemen employing the principal component methodology. They discovered that trade openness and economic expansion had a favourable effect on the rate of financial development. Being dependent on natural resources has detrimental effects.

Takyi and Obeng (2013) also used an auto-regressive distributed lag model to identify the factors that influenced Ghana's financial progress. According to the model's estimation purposes, trade openness and per capita income both significantly and positively impacted a nation's ability to advance financially. Reserve necessities for financial institutions have a detrimental statistically significant affect in both the short and long term, but inflation and interest rates have a positive statistically significant impact. On the contrary, spending by governments has little impact. Benya (2010) found a strong positive correlation between trade openness and financial development. Huang (2005) asserts that financial development benefits from political liberalization, particularly in the near term. Assefa (2014) used a supply-side technique to assess the short- and long-term effects of macroeconomic parameters, bank-specific factors, and monetary regulation on bank loans to the private sector in Ethiopia. The rule, the author found, has no long-term or short-term impact on commercial lending loans to the business community.

Applying yearly time series data from 1995 to 2014, Bist and Read (2018a) used panel co-integration analysis to examine the long-term connection between financial growth and economic expansion in 16 nations with low incomes. The outcome of the dynamic OLS estimation demonstrates that financial stability significantly and favourably influences the growth of the economy. Ellahi (Ellahi et al., 2021) investigated the institutional elements influencing the South Asian Association of Regional Cooperation (SAARC) region's financial sector. Using the generalized method of moment, the author discovered that financial strength is statistically positively and significantly impacted by trade openness, governmental characteristics, legal origin, and real gross domestic product. However, inflation has a very detrimental impact. Numerous elements that either beneficial or detrimentally impact the Report Phrase finance-growth relationship were covered in recent studies. The influence of inflation on the connection between finance and economic growth in the West African region was investigated by Ehigiamusoe et al. (2019). They discovered an adverse relationship between financial development and the price index. Determining the inflation threshold, which was 5.6% above and would be detrimental to the association, is a novel finding. Important research revealed that it is preferable to enhance financial development while lowering the rate of inflation rather than raising both. An identical study was conducted in 2019 by Ehigiamusoe et al., who examined the importance of macroeconomic stability in determining financial development. The analysis of the West African region revealed that macroeconomic stability is crucial, especially for enlargement of financial sphere.

METHODOLOGY

This research study is going to use panel data for the selected dependent and independent variables in annual time-series data bases in case of chosen four Central Asian countries such as, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Tajikistan and Uzbekistan. Private credit to percentage of GDP is taken as a dependent variable for this study and below deep statistic information regarding to other dependent variables are delivered in deep. Clarifying an appropriate methodology for any particular research paper is so crucial in terms of examining the relationship between endogenous and exogenous variables in case of a certain interest area. In addition to this, accuracy of the model is also important since the results can be employed as an inference for some particular conditions. That is why many researchers struggle to employ an appropriate model for their studies so as to rise the accuracy and unbiasedness of the outcomes. After many affords and considerations, the implication of Simple linear regression analysis for panel data is argued as final method for examining the impact of selected independent variables on financial development in case of above-mentioned countries group and below the general equation of the model is provided as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{Financial_development}_i \\ &= \beta_0 + \beta_1 TO_i + \beta_2 GDP_per_cap_i + \beta_3 Inflation_i \\ &+ \beta_4 Policy_rate_i + \beta_5 Reserve_requirement_i + \beta_6 Gov_debt_i + \varepsilon_i. \end{aligned}$$

As stated in equation above, financial development which is standing for dependent variable is explained by collecting data for private credit by banks in percentage of GDP during the period of 2009 and 2023. Determinants are collected based on macroeconomic and financial factors. To be more accurate, for macroeconomic factors data for inflation, GDP per cap-and-trade openness is taken while for financial and monetary system data for policy rate, reserve requirement and government debt in percentage of GDP has been taken in order to explain the influence factor of them on alteration of financial growth in case of focused country group throughout the period. It is vital to note that, conducting the simple linear regression is not enough for giving an inference about the role of those factors on financial development without conducting a relevant test for post estimations such as checking multicollinearity, heteroskedasticity and endogeneity issues that are considered as common model estimation problems in investigation of panel data. Statistical conclusions about those post estimations are also involved in the.

Empirical results.

Outcome of simple linear regression is going to be explained in this paragraph and there can be chance to compare the findings of previous conducted the same studies. Based on the regression table below, one-point changes in trade openness leads to reduction of financial development by 1.33 percent but this is found as not statistically significant since standard error is much higher than predicted coefficient as seen below. If annual value of GDP per cap changes by one thousand USD, this leads to accelerate financial development by 0.3 percent and the impact of this factor is found as statistically significant at one percent significance level. The result of inflation has represented somehow contradictory influence on financial development, under this study one percent changes of inflation results in rise of financial development by 0.522 percent and it is considered as statistically significant at five percent significance level. However, as mentioned earlier, studies of Robinson (2015) and Patrick (2016) claimed that, inflation is considered as one of the factors which causes to have opposite direction effect on financial development. Further variable policy rate which is standing for refinancing

rate of each country's central bank and if refinancing rate changes by one percent this follows to rise of financial development by 0.039 percent but it is found as not statistically significant. The impact of reserve requirement rate observed as having negative on banking development. To be more accurate, one percent changes in the value of reserve requirement leads to slowdown of financial development by (0.485) percent and it is statistically significant at five percent significance level. On top of that, the effect of government debt is found to be positive and one percent changes in the value of government debt in share of GDP leads to rise of financial development by 0.292 percent and it is statistically significant at one percent significance level.

Linear regression

Financial_developm~t	Coef.	St. Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf	Interval]	Sig
TO	-1.332	3.987	-0.33	.74	-9.33	6.665	
GDP_per_cap	.003	.000	8.17	.000	.002	.003	***
Inflation	.522	.238	2.20	.032	.045	.999	**
Policy_rate	.039	.174	0.23	.823	-.311	.389	
Reserve_requirement	-.485	.198	-2.45	.018	-.881	-.088	**
Gov_debt	.292	.062	4.68	.000	.167	.417	***
Constant	2.812	5.585	0.50	.617	-8.391	14.014	
Mean dependent var	22.082		SD dependent var	11.389			
R-squared	0.741		Number of obs	60			
F-test	25.331		Prob > F	0.000			
Akaike crit. (AIC)	394.024		Bayesian crit. (BIC)	408.685			

*** p<.01, ** p<.05, * p<.1

After regression analysis, conducting a number of post estimation tests is important in order to make sure whether the inference of coefficients to population is reliable or not. One of the common issues is observing heteroskedasticity problem in linear regression. Prior to explain the result of Breusch-Pagan test, providing illustration about heteroskedasticity can be logical. Variables can be constant in time changes or non-constant as time changes, if the former cases observed the variables are considered as homoskedasticity while the latter case noticed the variables are not constant and it is called heteroskedasticity issue. There are a number of methods to check heteroskedasticity of variables such as, Bruesch-Pagan test, graphical explanation and technical method. The test below Breusch-Pagan test and it is common in examining the heteroskedasticity issue in the model and based on the chi-square and p-value, we are able to accept null hypothesis which claims about homoskedasticity of variables namely the variables are constant in time changes at five percent significance level. In appendix, scatter graph and technical explanations are provided. In general condition, while Breusch-pagan test considered as the variables are constant, in most cases many models are suffer from difference of residuals time by time. It means that, there will be error between fitted value and population which is explained with residuals. There are a number of methods are proposed to solve this issue and obtain the best linear regression results as possible as. For this, implication of some advanced models can be requested by increasing sample size based on critical value of variance change.

** Heteroskedasticity **

Breusch-Pagan / Cook-Weisberg test for heteroskedasticity

Ho: Constant variance

Variables: fitted values of financial development

chi2(1) = 3.17

Prob > chi2 = 0.0749

Further common model related issue is witnessed with occurrence of multicollinearity between variables. If the variables are integrated with each other more than 0.5 percent this is argued as there is similar variable participation in the model and this might lead to have biased regression result. Thus, in order to check whether the model is suffering from multicollinearity or not, a number of tests are used in common, and one of those tests is Breusch-Godfrey test below. In response to the outcome of test, it can be concluded that, the variables are not correlated with each other with high percentage and model is considered as free from multicollinearity issue since average value of vif test below is lower than five, while some econometric coursebooks marked this value as ten, in many research scientists take the average value of vif test at five which is border for claiming existence of high correlation risk within variables in the model.

Multicollinearity test

VIF	1/VIF
2.310	0.432
1.920	0.521
1.830	0.545
1.730	0.577
1.520	0.660
1.250	0.798

1.760

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

To make the growth of economy stable and rise the social well-fare of individuals the development of financial sphere is so important. Nevertheless, financial sectors of Central Asian countries are not desired due to some restrictions and puzzles which are pivotal to find the solution of them so as to support economic growth. There are not many researches and empirical examination regarding to financial condition of Central Asian countries. Thus, identifying some determinant factors of financial development in case of Central Asian countries has paramount importance. Hence, the major objective of this study was to examine determinant factors of selected countries' financial sector development. To achieve this objective panel data based on annual time interval from 2009 and 2023 in each selected four countries case has been collected. Several databases were employed to collect data, it is irrefutable that, world bank was the major database for macroeconomic variables while for financial variables each country's central banks was targeted to get data throughout the period. For the purpose of examine the influence of determinant factors of financial development, simple linear regression model is used and according to outcomes, trade openness, reserve requirement was found to have

adverse effect while the remaining variables revealed positive influence on financial development at one and five percent significance level.

Central Asian governments and central banks have the authority to modify their regulations regarding lending and saving interest rates. Raising the interest rate on savings will encourage people to deposit money with financial institutions, enabling them to have sufficient funds to provide loans. Lending interest rates would be lowered by the relevant authority in order to balance supply and demand for loanable funds.

An attempt should be made to promote increased trade openness by lowering trade barriers and streamlining procedures and regulations in order to enable high and sustained development of the financial sector performance in focused economies. However, for less developed nations like Kyrgyzstan, Tajikistan, and Uzbekistan, which are heavily dependent on international commerce, this could be harmful to economic growth as the Prebisch-Singer law states that terms of trade decrease. Trade openness, which is determined by dividing the GDP by the total of imports and exports, can therefore be increased by lending enough money to export sectors, which will diversify and make it easier for the export of produced and semi-finished goods, which will lead to financial growth.

In addition to this, marking reserve requirement at high rate can also be restriction for financial development of countries. This is because, if reserve rates continue to grow, this might cause to close the circulation of such an amount of budget in an economy by just keeping it in balance of banks. Undoubtedly, we are away from initiating zero rate of reserve request, there must be a certain amount of reserve in each bank balance, but this must not be high because money under the pillow is considered as dead money as they are not contributing rise of economic circulation. Thus, this process must be controlled by central banks in order to keep the balance of both reserve and loans by banks.

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